

Supplementary Material

Manifold Learning for Real-World Event Understanding

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I. SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

A. Datasets Construction

Specific criteria used to construct the three For Ablation Analysis datasets:

- **Wedding:** Representative videos present the royal wedding between Prince William and Catherine Middleton placed in Westminster Abbey on 29 April 2011. Non-Representative / VC are videos presenting other royal weddings (all placed in Westminster Abbey), other events with prince William or/and Catherine Middleton. Non-Representative / C includes videos from normal weddings, other churches, dolls of the prince and Catherine, and a parody of the wedding. Non-Representative / F are videos which could not be included in the other categories. Examples of each of the categories are presented in Figure S1;
- **Fire:** Representative videos present the Notre Dame Cathedral fire which happened on 15 April 2019. Non-Representative / VC are videos presenting the same cathedral in different periods of time before the fire. Non-Representative / C includes videos from other gothic cathedrals around Europe and other accidents involving buildings on fire. Non-Representative / F are videos which could not be included in the other categories. Examples of each of the categories are presented in Figure S2;
- **Bombing:** Representative videos present the Boston Marathon Bombing which occurred on 15 April 2013. Non-Representative / VC are videos presenting Boston Marathons in other years. Non-Representative / C includes videos from other marathons and other explosions. Non-Representative / F are videos that could not be included in the other categories. Examples of each of the categories are presented in Figure S3;

Table S1 presents the subdivisions of images in the test set for the FCA datasets (*Wedding*, *Fire* and *Bombing*). This division intends to simulate different setups where there is more or less Very Close (VC) and Close (C) Non-Representative images to disturb the retrieval process.

B. Experiment I: exploring network depth and width

The first experiment evaluates the performance of different depth/width in the combination network. Figures S4, and S5 present the results of this experiment for the solutions trained with cross-entropy and contrastive, respectively. $N(512, 128)$

Dataset	Representative	Non-Representative categories			
		VC	C	F	Total
<i>Wedding</i>	84	587	3,565	2,286	6,522
<i>Fire</i>	390	182	7,217	1,021	8,810
<i>Bombing</i>	320	0	3,216	3,214	6,750

TABLE S1

Wedding, *Fire* and *Bombing* BREAKDOWN IN THE TEST SETS CONSIDERING THE REPRESENTATIVE AND THE NON-REPRESENTATIVE SUBCLASSES (VERY CLOSE (VC), CLOSE (C) AND FAR (F)).

and $N(1024, 512)$ present the best precision rates in datasets with less training images as *Wedding* dataset, and also for the training sets without augmentation (first column of the figures). The networks trained with cross-entropy loss presented consistency in relation to the best performances of $N(512, 128)$ and $N(1024, 512)$.

The networks with less layers in the *Combination* part performed better, possibly due to the small quantities of required training samples. We select both $N(512, 128)$ and $N(1024, 512)$ networks for the next experiment in which we explore their behavior with different training set sizes.

C. Experiment II: varying training quantities

Figures S7 and S8 show the obtained results when training the networks with small quantities of original representative images, using cross-entropy and contrastive, respectively. In this case, we compare $N(512, 128)$ and $N(1024, 512)$ to the semi-supervised method ESS [1]. Even with reduced quantities of training images, the components combination $N(512, 128)$ and $N(1024, 512)$ produced the best MAP results, resulting in an improvement of more than 10 percentage points in the smallest set (with only 10 representative images). We also notice a significant performance improvement for both $N(512, 128)$ and $N(1024, 512)$, with slightly superior results for $N(1024, 512)$. In view of these results, we continue the experiments adopting the $N(1024, 512)$ network as our standard option.

D. Experiment III: visualizing classes separation

As we chose the combination network $N(1024, 512)$, we intended to analyze how the images were projected onto a 2-dimensional space, verifying if the combination provides better separation between classes than the baseline approaches. Figure S9 presents the projection of all images of the datasets

(a) Event

(b) Queen Elizabeth II and Prince Phillip (VC)

(c) Event Parody (C)

(d) Non-Related (F)

(a) Event

(b) Cathedral before fire (VC)

(c) Other gothic cathedral (C)

(d) Non-Related (F)

Fig. S1. Examples of each category and subcategory of dataset *Wedding*. Frames extracted from YouTube videos: (a) KmKGzspzg0I, (b) BEfixFk57EE, (c) GTrpwXODmZo, (d) 0BtyjVqU8yE (Last accessed on March 10, 2021).

Fig. S2. Examples of each category and subcategory of dataset *Fire*. Frames extracted from YouTube videos: (a) VgIjqm1rfJw (ABC News), (b) and (c) 2VRQWyoRx6U, (d) dqCcM2sgTQw (Last accessed on March 10, 2021).

onto the learned spaces without data augmentation techniques, using the Representative and Non-Representative classes. We notice a similar behavior in the classification approaches — *Pre-trained*, *Fine-Tuned* and *Cross-Entropy* — and even for ESS, presenting more dispersion of images from both classes. On the other hand, the distance-learning approaches — *Contrastive* and *Triplet* — present much better separations, tightly grouping images from each class.

In Figure S9, if we consider the different non-purple colors

as the levels VC, C and F, we could perform an analysis of the different levels of non-representativeness with and without data augmentation. The manifolds constructed by *Contrastive* and *Triplet* approaches apparently better separate the Non-Representative images from the Representative ones. These two classes represent the semantics observed in the images, and we expected them to be more distant in the projection space.

Based on the visualizations, we could observe that possibly

(a) Event

(b) Boston Marathon 2018 (VC)

(c) Tokyo Marathon 2019 (C)

(d) Non-Related (F)

Fig. S3. Examples of each category and subcategory of dataset *Bombing*. Frames extracted from YouTube videos: (a) IdDsAsvUunA, (b) BE6nuOcbMck, (c) 9aABH_0xcxI, (d) FkVYJQDoi7w (Last accessed on March 10, 2021).

the distance-learning approaches are able to better separate Representative from Non-Representative images, especially when using the augmented data for training. To verify the performance in the retrieval task, we move now to the fourth experiment, by retrieving Representative images based on the six methods we assess in the paper.

E. Experiment IV: retrieving representative images

The results of the rankings are also supported by the mean distance of the images from Representative and Non-Representative classes. Figure S10 presents the mean and variance of the image distances to queries in the *Wedding*, *Fire* and *Bombing* datasets. In this experiment, we expect Representative images to be closer to the queries (lower mean). For this reason, a good result here would show Representative images with lower mean and variance. As expected, the three proposed methods (*Cross-Entropy*, *Contrastive* and *Triplet*), show a lower mean distance for Representative images (with lower variance) than the mean distances for the Non-Representative images. The obtained results indicate that learning a proper combination manifold allows a better separation of representative and non-representative images of an event.

F. Experiment V: ranking visual quality

Finally, as we aim for a better-separated space, we expect to be able to see differences among the top-retrieved images, using different types of features. For this qualitative analysis, we observed the obtained rankings presented in Figures S11 and S12 for *Wedding* and *Fire* datasets, respectively. The first row denotes the query. It is followed by the retrieved the images using *Concatenated*, *ESS*, *Fine-Tuned*, *Cross-Entropy*, *Contrastive* and *Triplet* in each column (*top@5*), respectively. The purple squares indicate the representative images while the green squares denote the non-representative ones. Note how the manifolds learned by the component combination (proposed methods) provide more discriminative features, improving the precision and diversity of top positions. *Contrastive* and *Triplet* present the best rankings in this case.

G. Experiment VI: data augmentation

The previous experiment results presented the basis for choosing the configuration of our networks. Now we aim to compare the results of using the best obtained representations for a classification task observing the impact of data augmentation during training. We chose to use the representations generated by the combination networks with *Contrastive* and *Triplet* losses as they outperformed the other representations in the retrieval task.

We selected two simple classifiers for this experiment: a *Multilayer Perceptron Classifier* (MLP) [3] and a *Support Vector Machine Classifier* (SVC) [4]. For the MLP Classifier, we used one hidden layer with 64 neurons, *tanh* as activation function and adaptive learning rate with initial learning rate equal to 0.001. We trained until convergence or reaching 1,000 iterations. For SVC, we used the RBF kernel with parameter $C = 1.0$. For both methods, we used the same training sets used to train the manifolds previously presented.

According to the results presented in Figure S13, the Balanced Accuracy is improved by augmentation, especially for small datasets as *Wedding*. For two datasets, *Wedding* and *Bombing*, augmentation also improves the F1-Measure.

For both retrieval (Sections IV-A, IV-C, and IV-D) and classification, augmentation is critical when few training samples are available. For this reason, all experiments hereinafter include data augmentation for training.

Fig. S4. Results of training networks with cross-entropy loss. Networks $N(512, 128)$ and $N(1024, 512)$ presented the best precision for almost all the training sets. The first column shows results for non-augmented data while the second shows results for the augmented sets.

H. Experiment VII: varying training sizes for classification

For this experiment, similar to Experiment II (Section I-VB), we reduced the size of training sets, in this case for the classification task. We randomly selected 10 images, 25% of training (including the 10 images of the small set) and 50% of training (including the 25% of the previous set), and compared with the complete training set. We included the augmented images for all the training sets.

The results in Figures S16, S14, and S15 revealed two key findings; (i) F1-measure performance and balanced accuracy, that is the model generalization, improved with increasing size of training sets and (ii) in most cases, it is only necessary to have 50% of the training size used to achieve a good result, even some of the behaviors got worse with the use of the 100% of training size (see the balanced accuracy in Figure S16). Similar observations were made in the triplet results for the *Fire* dataset in Figure S15. Certainly, increasing the size of training sets could lead to robust predictions. However, we can affirm that our proposed methods require medium sets sizes

when trained to get a satisfactory result, and our findings have implications for practical applications of them.

I. Experiment VIII: comparing different methods

For consultation, we present in Figure S17 the precision values for the new datasets (*National Museum* and *Bangladesh Fire*) using the *Contrastive* and *Triplet* approaches. We performed the retrieval using the representative training images as queries (including augmentation) to retrieve relevant images from the test set. The results presented evince the quality of the representations obtained.

In order to provide an alternative way of results presentation (also presented in Figures 13 and 14), we provide Table S2 with the Balanced Accuracy and F1-measure for the five datasets during the comparison among the proposed approaches and the state-of-the-art methods.

We also present here examples of rankings generated using the *Contrastive* and *Triplet* representation. We intend to retrieve the most similar $top@25$ images to a query (Figure S18)

Fig. S5. Results of training networks with contrastive loss. Network $N(1024, 512)$ presented the best precision for two datasets even without augmentation techniques. All the networks presented similar results for the augmented training sets. The first column shows results for non-augmented data while the second shows results for the augmented sets.

	Wedding		Fire		Bombing		Museum		Bangladesh	
	Balanced Accuracy	F1-Measure								
Proposed-Contrastive	0.70	0.48	0.74	0.31	0.83	0.62	0.93	0.92	0.92	0.89
Proposed-Contrastive (SVM)	0.74	0.53	0.74	0.33	0.84	0.61	0.92	0.91	0.91	0.90
Proposed-Triplet	0.78	0.25	0.75	0.27	0.81	0.58	0.92	0.91	0.94	0.94
Proposed-Triplet (SVM)	0.80	0.26	0.75	0.23	0.80	0.59	0.92	0.91	0.96	0.94
Fewshot-RelationNet Cross	0.50	0.02	0.49	0.07	0.49	0.07	0.53	0.49	0.57	0.51
Fewshot-RelationNet Trained	0.59	0.02	0.55	0.10	0.52	0.09	0.52	0.27	0.60	0.47
CAMLP	0.76	0.08	0.73	0.20	0.66	0.16	0.96	0.95	0.92	0.89
MAD	0.74	0.08	0.77	0.28	0.70	0.20	1.00	1.00	0.89	0.87
sGAN	0.50	0.00	0.51	0.09	0.52	0.64	0.50	0.00	0.67	0.68

TABLE S2

A DIFFERENT PRESENTATION OF RESULTS FROM FIGURES 13 AND 14. THE VALUES OF BALANCED ACCURACY AND F1-MEASURE ARE COMPARED FOR THE FIVE DATASET AND DIFFERENT LEARNING TECHNIQUES.

from the unlabeled test of the datasets *Museum* (Figure S19) composed by 490 images, and *Bangladesh* (Figure S20) composed by 759 images.

REFERENCES

- [1] C. M. Rodrigues, L. Pereira, A. Rocha, and Z. Dias, "Image semantic representation for event understanding," in *11th IEEE International Workshop on Information Forensics and Security (WIFS)*. IEEE, 2019, pp. 1–6.
- [2] L. McInnes, J. Healy, and J. Melville, "Umap: Uniform manifold approximation and projection for dimension reduction," 2018. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1802.03426>

Fig. S6. Results of training networks with triplet loss. Network $N(1024,512)$ presented the best precision for two events (the smaller datasets: *Wedding* and *Fire*) without considering augmentation techniques, which indicates the possibility of training shallower networks with few training samples. The first column shows results for non-augmented data while the second shows results for the augmented sets.

- [3] G. E. Hinton, "Connectionist learning procedures," *Artificial Intelligence*, vol. 40, no. 1, pp. 185 – 234, 1989.
- [4] J. C. Platt, "Probabilistic outputs for support vector machines and comparisons to regularized likelihood methods," *Advances in Large Margin Classifiers*, pp. 61–74, 1999.

Fig. S7. MAP results for networks with cross-entropy loss with small training sets. $N(512, 128)$ and $N(1024, 512)$ presented similar behavior outperforming the ESS MAP results even for very small training sets (i.e., ten representative images).

Fig. S8. MAP results for networks with contrastive loss with small training sets. $N(512, 128)$ and $N(1024, 512)$ presented similar behavior outperforming the ESS MAP results even for the very small training sets (i.e., ten representative images).

Fig. S9. Scatter plots of Representative (purple circles), Non-Representative VC (lime-green x's – really small quantity), Non-Representative C (light green circles), and Non-Representative F (dark green circles) images of all datasets into learned spaces without data augmentation. The dimensionality of the samples were reduced using *Uniform Manifold Approximation and Projection (UMAP)* [2] in order to visualize. This four-class visualization highlights the capacity of the *Triplet* learned space to depart the Non-Representative F from the Representative images.

Fig. S10. Distance mean and variance of images from each class of the test set to the queries in *Wedding*, *Fire* and *Bombing* datasets, without considering data augmentation techniques. It is expected that Non-Representative images have considerable bigger distances than Representative ones. Each horizontal set of bars is proportional to its small value in order to facilitate visualization.

Fig. S11. Comparison of top results for the different methods. Rankings obtained using the learned manifolds – *Cross-Entropy*, *Contrastive* and *Triplet* – presented better precision and variability in the *top@5* positions. The first row presents the query image followed by the *top@5* retrieved images (in the columns) for the *Wedding* dataset. Purple-border images denote Representative images and green-border images denote Non-Representative ones.

Fig. S12. Comparison of top results for the different methods. Rankings obtained using the learned manifolds – *Cross-Entropy*, *Contrastive* and *Triplet* – presented better precision and variability in the $top@5$ positions. The first row presents the query image followed by the $top@5$ retrieved images (in the columns) for *Fire* dataset. Purple-border images denote Representative images and green-border images denote Non-Representative ones.

Fig. S13. Balanced accuracy and F1 measure for the datasets *Bombing*, *Wedding*, and *Fire*, considering a not augmented dataset (bars with pure color), and augmented dataset (bars with a dashed pattern). Balanced Accuracy is improved by augmentation, especially for small datasets as *Wedding*. For two datasets, *Wedding* and *Bombing*, augmentation also improves the F1-Measure.

Fig. S14. Balanced accuracy and f1 measure of our proposed methods applied in the *Wedding* dataset, varying the training set size. We randomly selected 10 images, 25% of training (including the 10 images of the small set) and 50% of training (including the 25% of the previous set), and compared with the complete training set.

Fig. S15. Balanced accuracy and f1 measure of our proposed methods applied in the *Fire* dataset, varying the training set size. We randomly selected 10 images, 25% of training (including the 10 images of the small set) and 50% of training (including the 25% of the previous set), and compared with the complete training set.

Fig. S16. Balanced accuracy and f1 measure of our proposed methods applied in the *Bombing* dataset, varying the training set size. We randomly selected 10 images, 25% of training (including the 10 images of the small set) and 50% of training (including the 25% of the previous set), and compared with the complete training set.

Fig. S17. Values of precision by recall points for the new datasets: *National Museum* and *Bangladesh Fire*. We compare the representations obtained by the Contrastive and Triplet approaches for both datasets.

(a) Query for *Museum* dataset

(b) Query for *Bangladesh* dataset

Fig. S18. Examples of queries used to retrieve the two Not Analysed Before datasets. The queries were used for generating rankings of Figures S19 and S20 of *Museum* and *Bangladesh* respectively. Images obtained from: (a) <https://t.co/QN4Z99cSAR> (Accessed on February 21, 2019) and (b) <https://t.co/LXnuHtfXZA> (BBC News) (Accessed on September 03, 2018).

(b) Ranking using *Triplet* representation

Fig. S19. *Top@25* images retrieved from unlabeled test of *Museum* dataset (among 490 images) using *Contrastive* (figure (a)) and *Triplet* (figure (b)) representations, and Figure S18(a) as query.

(b) Ranking using *Triplet* representation

Fig. S20. *Top@25* images retrieved from unlabeled test of *Bangladesh* dataset (among 759 images) using *Contrastive* (figure (a)) and *Triplet* (figure (b)) representations, and Figure S18(b) as query.